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P2Y₁₂ receptor antagonists and AR receptor agonists regulates Protein Disulfide Isomerase secretion from platelets and endothelial cells

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ABSTRACT

Secretion of PDI from platelets and endothelial cells is an important step of all thrombotic events. In the absence of extracellular PDI thrombus formation and fibrin generation may be impaired. Thrombin-mediated PDI secretion is regulated by the stimulation of P2Y₁₂ receptors. This paper provides evidences that P2Y₁₂ antagonists or AR agonists may modulate release of PDI molecules from platelets and with less efficiency from endothelial cells. Moreover P2Y₁₂ antagonization or AR agonization modulates platelet-endothelial interaction. We prove that combinations of P2Y₁₂ antagonists and AR agonists inhibit platelet-dependent adhesion of cancer cells to endothelium and attenuate cancer cell invasiveness, but longer exposition to AR agonists may stimulate migration of invasive breast cancer cells through endothelium thus leading to increased metastasis.

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1. Introduction

Modification of thiol-disulfide balance is important step during platelets activation. Changes in platelet activation may result in 440% increase in surface protein thiol groups. During platelet activation the number of Protein Disulfide Isomerase molecules on the cell surface dramatically increases and reduction of the disulfide bonds on PDI occurs. This leads to conformational changes in GP1ba and integrins, potential targets for enzymatic activity of PDI [1,2]. After laser-induced arteriolar injury a time-dependent increase in PDI secretion is observed. Blocking antibodies against PDI inhibit platelet thrombus formation and fibrin generation in mice [3].

Platelets are not the only source of PDI circulating in the blood. PDI is secreted from activated endothelial cells in contact with plasma or after injury of the vessel wall. PDI molecules are found in the site of the injury even in the absence of platelet accumulation. Normal fibrin generation can be observed after incubation with inhibitors of platelet aggregation but not after PDI antibodies [4]. Impaired release of PDI from platelets and endothelial cells may be

caused by the deficiency in ADP level, as a result of the defect in T granules secretion and decreased sensitivity to thrombin, like in the Hermansky-Pudlak syndrome [5]. Main targets of secreted PDI include integrin α IIb β 3 on platelets [6] and integrin α V β 3 on endothelial cells [7], which are responsible for cells adhesion and migration on ECM proteins [8]. Other potential substrates for PDI enzymatic activity include vitronectin [9], tissue factor [10], factor XI [11], C4b-binding protein, α 2-macroglobulin, CD5 antigen-like protein [12].

ADP is released from platelets and serves as a direct activator or as an enhancer of platelet response to other activating factors. Platelets have two ADP receptors: the P2Y₁ and P2Y₁₂, which is the main target for ADP-dependent anti-platelet therapy [13] including thienopyridine inhibitors i.e. prasugrel [14] or the ATP analogue – cangrelor [15]. Adenosine receptors (AR) belong to a family of G protein-coupled receptors that regulate a wide spectrum of physiological processes. Only A_{2A} and A_{2B} receptors can be found on platelets surface [16]. Since ligand binding to A_{2A} and A_{2B} receptors leads to increased production of intracellular cAMP, which results in the inhibition of platelets activation [17], adenosine analogues are used in anti-platelet therapy [18].

Endothelial cells, unlike platelets, respond to either thienopyridine metabolites or thienopyridines as ADP receptor blockers, which causes reduced proliferation, increased production of ECM proteins and release of vasoactive factors [19]. P2Y₁₂ antagonists

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may also contribute to anti-neoplastic and anti-angiogenic mechanisms. Endothelial cells constitutively produce adenosine at sites of vascular injury thus regulating activation of coagulation process [20]. Endothelial cells after incubation with thrombin secrete adenosine nucleotides then converted to adenosine. AR agonization modulates thrombin-mediated proinflammatory responses [21].

Since AR agonists enhance the anti-platelet effect of P2Y₁₂ inhibitors and potentially overcome resistance to P2Y₁₂ antagonists in an anti-platelet therapy [22], the aim of this study was to evaluate if P2Y₁₂ inhibition, AR agonization or both of these processes combined, can affect crucial step of thrombus formation, which is PDI secretion from platelets or endothelial cells.

2. Materials and methods

Cell cultures – EA.hy926 and HMEC-1 cells were cultured as described previously [23]. MDA-MB-231 cells were cultured using Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 with 10% FBS and LoVo cells were cultured using Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) with 10% FBS in a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere at 37 °C.

Blood collection – Experiments were approved by the Ethics of Research in Human Experimentation Committee at the Medical University of Lodz, approval number (RNN/43/17/KE). After having received written consents from volunteers, blood was collected from healthy donors, who had not taken medications known to influence platelet function for at least two weeks, into a vacuum tube containing 0.105 mol/l buffered sodium citrate, with the final citrate: blood ratio of 1:9 vol/vol.

Platelet preparation – Platelets were isolated as described previously [24] by a two-step centrifugation at 37 °C: first 200×g for 12 min to obtain platelet rich plasma (PRP), and subsequent centrifugation of PRP at 800×g for 15 min, and re-suspension of platelet pellet with Tyrode's buffer (134 mM NaCl, 12 mM NaHCO₃, 2.9 mM KCl, 0.34 mM Na₂HPO₄, 1 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 5 mM glucose, pH to 7.4) to desired platelet density.

PDI secretion – Secretion of PDI from endothelial cells and platelets was performed as described previously [25]. Incubation with thrombin (0.5 U/ml) was performed by simultaneously incubation with P2Y₁₂ antagonists or AR agonists.

Cell-cell adhesion – adhesion of MDA-MB-231 and LoVo cells was performed as described previously [23]. Before adhesion tested factors were pre-incubated with endothelial cells for 15 min and added directly to cancer cells. Adhesion of cancer cells with the addition of platelets include co-incubation of MDA-MB-231 or LoVo (4×10^5 cells/ml) with platelets (2×10^8 cells/ml) in serum free RPMI 1640 for 15 min at 37 °C and then transfer of cancer cells and platelets into plates at a count of 2×10^5 cells/well followed by adhesion to the endothelium for 1 h.

Platelet adhesion to endothelium – adhesion of platelets to endothelium monolayer was performed similarly to cancer cell adhesion. Platelets at a count of 2×10^8 cells/ml resuspended in RPMI 1640 with 1%BSA were stained for 10 min at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. The stained platelets were incubated with thrombin and the tested factors for 5 min. After incubation platelets were transferred into plates at a count of 1×10^8 cells/well and allowed to adhere to the endothelium for 1 h.

Transendothelial migration – migration of MDA-MB-231 was performed as described previously [23]. Images were acquired with the use of fluorescence upright AxioExaminer.A1 microscope (Zeiss, Germany) equipped with Emc2 Rolera camera (QImaging, USA) and water-immersion lens $10 \times$.

3. Results

PDI secretion – Fig. 1 and Supplementary Figure figs1 shows that incubation with P2Y₁₂ antagonists: cangrelor AR-C69931MX (ARC) or prasugrel metabolite (PM) or with AR agonists: MRE0094, HE-NECA and NECA or combinations of these factors, does not affect PDI secretion from non-stimulated EA.hy926 cells. After stimulation with thrombin only ARC, MRE0094 and combination of these factors inhibit PDI release. Combination of P2Y₁₂ antagonists and AR agonists may decrease thrombin-dependent PDI secretion more potent than AR agonists themselves, but no cumulative effect is observed. Similar to EA.hy926, secretion of PDI from non-stimulated HMEC-1 cells was not affected by P2Y₁₂ antagonists or AR agonists. After thrombin stimulation both ARC and PM or combinations of these factors with HE-NECA and MRE0094 inhibit release of PDI. From AR agonists only MRE0094 shows tendency to attenuate PDI secretion without P2Y₁₂ antagonization (Supplementary Figure figs2).

Fig. 2 shows that thrombin-dependent PDI secretion from platelets can be blocked by HE-NECA and MRE0094 but not NECA, despite the fact that NECA slightly decreases PDI secretion. Both P2Y₁₂ antagonists inhibit releasing of PDI molecules and addition of P2Y₁₂ antagonists to AR agonists exhibits higher effectiveness in blocking of PDI secretion than AR agonists themselves, but cumulative effect was not observed.

Cell-cell adhesion and platelet adhesion to endothelium – Adhesion of thrombin-stimulated platelets to endothelial cells can be attenuated by all tested factors (Fig. 3 A, Supplementary Figure figs3). The most potent inhibitor of platelet adhesion to EA.hy926 cells is ARC and combination of ARC with MRE0094 or HE-NECA. During adhesion of stimulated platelets to HMEC-1, combination of P2Y₁₂ antagonist and AR agonists decreases platelet adhesion more effective than AR agonists. Only combination of ARC with HE-NECA or NECA seems to be more effective than ARC itself, but without significant difference between ARC and combinations of ARC with AR agonists.

Adhesion of cancer cells in the presence of platelets can be attenuated by P2Y₁₂ antagonist and AR agonists (Fig. 3 B, Supplementary Figure figs4). The most potent inhibitor of MDA-MB-231 or LoVo adhesion to HMEC-1 is PM, which also reduces level of adhesion observed after incubation with AR agonists. However, additive effect of any combination was not observed.

Cancer cells adhesion to endothelium in the absence of platelets is less sensitive to P2Y₁₂ antagonization or AR agonization (Supplementary Figure figs5). Adhesion of MDA-MB-231 to EA.hy926 can be blocked by ARC and PM, when adhesion do HMEC-1 can be attenuated only by PM. NECA increases breast cancer adhesion to endothelium and addition of P2Y₁₂ antagonists only slightly affects this process (Fig. 4 A). Adhesion of LoVo to endothelium can be attenuated by ARC and PM, but adhesion to HMEC-1 can be additionally blocked by HE-NECA, NECA and combination of them with P2Y₁₂ antagonists (Fig. 4. B). Transendothelial migration of MDA-MB-231 cells through HMEC-1 monolayer can be attenuated by both P2Y₁₂ antagonists with similar efficiency. All tested AR agonists stimulate migration of breast cancer cells, but addition of PM or ARC inhibits MRE0094, HE-NECA or NECA-stimulated migration (Fig. 4. C, Supplementary Figure figs6).

4. Discussion

Effectiveness of anti-platelet therapy depends on reduced sensitivity to anti-platelet agents observed in many patients. Increased drug doses contribute to higher risk of bleeding and to reduce this risk combined administration of different anti-platelet drugs is applied. Such approach involving combination of P2Y₁₂

Fig. 1. PDI secretion from endothelial cells EA.hy926 without (A) or with 0.5 U/ml thrombin (B). Densitometry analysis was performed using the National Institute of Health (NIH) ImageJ software. Data presented as mean \pm SEM, $n = 10$. Significance of differences was analysed with two-way ANOVA and Bonferroni's post-test to compare replicate means.

antagonists and AR agonists provides higher efficiency of inhibition of platelet activation than the P2Y₁₂ antagonist alone [22].

PDI molecules can be secreted from endothelial cells and platelets [4] during thrombotic events. Extracellular PDI in blood stream is often involved in activation of β 3 integrins [26] and blocking of PDI secretion can cause inhibition of platelet accumulation and fibrin generation [27].

In our study we examine if using of anti-platelet agents like P2Y₁₂ antagonists or AR agonists may contribute to diminished secretion of PDI from endothelium or platelets. Endothelial cells unlike platelets exhibit ability to constitutive secretion of PDI without other stimuli than presence of integrin ligands [28]. We observed that P2Y₁₂ antagonists or AR agonists display no effect on constitutive secretion of PDI in both tested cell lines: EA.hy926 and HMEC-1.

We show that stimulation of endothelial cells with thrombin leads to increased release of PDI than during constitutive secretion and this process can be attenuated by P2Y₁₂ antagonists: ARC or PM. Absence of ADP, which is the ligand for P2Y₁₂ receptors caused by dense granule deficiency, leads to impaired PDI release from platelets and endothelial cells in Hermansky-Pudlak syndrome. Decreased sensitivity to thrombin after ADP deficiency results in defective fibrin generation and lower platelet accumulation. Combination of ADP plus thrombin could restore normal PDI secretion and platelet aggregation in Hermansky-Pudlak mice [5]. Our study supports that findings proving that blocking P2Y₁₂ activation may contribute to inhibition of PDI secretion in response to thrombin.

However different endothelial cell lines express different sensitivity to P2Y₁₂ antagonists; EA.hy926 seems to be more sensitive for reversible ARC and HMEC-1 for irreversible PM. Direct effects of using P2Y₁₂ antagonists on endothelium are not fully elucidated. Ticagrelor, prasugrel and clopidogrel neither induced necrosis or apoptosis nor changed the endothelial cell viability, migration, invasiveness, wound healing and the production of VEGF, but they can reduce cell proliferation [29]. Endothelial cells respond to P2Y₁₂ antagonists, but P2Y₁₂ is probably not so widely expressed on endothelium like on platelets. It is even possible that some of endothelial cell lines do not express P2Y₁₂ at all and P2Y₁₂ antagonists affect these cells in nonspecific manner [30].

From tested AR agonists only MRE0094 decreases releasing of PDI molecules from EA.hy926 and HMEC-1 after incubation with thrombin. NECA is nonselective agonist for A_{2A} and A_{2B}, which may be the reason of its lower effectiveness. High affinity for A_{2A} receptor may be correlated with higher anti-aggregator properties like in the comparison of NECA and regadenoson [22,24], but affinity to different adenosine receptors cannot be only determining factor since nonselective LUF5835 does not exhibit anti-platelet properties comparable to NECA and does not inhibit platelet activation at all [22]. MRE0094 and HE-NECA are A_{2A} specific agonists. Higher blocking efficiency of MRE0094 in comparison to HE-NECA may be explained by different effectiveness of AR agonists, even if they are selective for single AR type. Different potency in inhibition of ADP-induced platelet aggregation was observed for different A_{2A} specific agonists, including MRE0094 [24].

Fig. 2. PDI secretion from platelets after stimulation with 0,5U/ml thrombin and incubation with MRE0094 (A), HE-NECA (B) and NECA (C). Densitometry analysis was performed using the National Institute of Health (NIH) ImageJ software. Data presented as mean ± SEM, n = 10. Significance of differences was analysed with two-way ANOVA and Bonferroni's post-test to compare replicate means.

Fig. 3. Adhesion of platelets to endothelial cells (A), adhesion of MDA-MB-231 and LoVo cells with the addition of platelets to endothelial cells (B) in the presence of P2Y₁₂ antagonists and AR agonists. Data presented as mean \pm SD; mini-max ranges marked as whiskers; $n = 10$. Significance of differences was analysed with one-way ANOVA and the post-hoc comparisons Dunnett's test.

We prove that platelets are more sensitive to P2Y₁₂ antagonists and AR agonists than endothelial cells. PDI secretion from platelets was blocked by all tested P2Y₁₂ antagonists or AR agonists with very high efficiency. Combined usage of P2Y₁₂ antagonists and AR agonists has similar effect on PDI secretion from thrombin-stimulated platelets and from thrombin-stimulated endothelial cells: no additive effect can be observed after using dual therapy. We assume that P2Y₁₂ antagonists inhibit PDI secretion by lowering sensitivity to thrombin in the way suggested by experiments on Hermansky-Pudlak mice [5]. Since AR agonists are rather ineffective in blocking PDI secretion from endothelium, but inhibit this process on platelets and they are known for blocking platelet activation by cAMP-dependent pathway [22], we suggest that inhibition of PDI secretion from platelets by AR agonists may be not related to ADP-mediated thrombin signalling or attenuates this process independently to P2Y₁₂ antagonists. This theory may also explain lack of additive effect of combined therapy, when addition of AR agonists does not lead to higher inhibition of PDI secretion, because maximum level of inhibition was achieved after incubation with P2Y₁₂ antagonists.

Interaction between different types of cells and endothelium may depend on integrin activation, which can be initiated by thiol-disulfide exchanges mediated by PDI [23]. Tested factors affect platelet adhesion to endothelium with different efficiency. During

adhesion to HMEC-1 combined usage of P2Y₁₂ antagonists and AR agonists is more effective than AR agonists alone. However, similar to PDI secretion we do not observe additive effect of combined therapy. This is unexpected observation since such approach proves to be effective in blocking platelet function: activation, aggregation and thrombus formation [22,24]. We theorize that lack of additive effect in combined therapy during platelet-endothelium interaction may be related to the conditions of the test, since AR agonists are less effective than P2Y₁₂ antagonist in blocking platelet activation under static conditions than in flow conditions [22]. Another explanation is that combined approach may be effective especially after ADP-stimulation [22,24] and strong platelet activator like thrombin overcomes blocking effect of AR agonists thus stimulating platelet activation and probably also PDI secretion.

Interaction between cancer cells and platelets is important for metastasis. The depletion of circulating platelets or inhibition of platelet activation decreases the metastatic potential of circulating tumor cells [31]. The role of ADP receptors in cancer metastasis is not clear. There is evidence for prasugrel-dependent increased risk in multiple types of solid tumors [32]. We are also aware of the findings suggesting that P2Y₁₂ deficiency reduced metastasis of pulmonary epithelial cells and platelet-induced EMT-like transformation [31]. P2Y₁₂ inhibitor ticagrelor attenuates lung or liver metastasis of melanoma and lung or bone marrow metastasis of

Fig. 4. Adhesion of MDA-MB-231 (A), LoVo (B) to endothelial cells. Transendothelial migration of MDA-MB-231 through HMEC-1 cells with the addition of tested factors (C). Data presented as mean \pm SD; mini-max ranges marked as whiskers; $n = 8$ for (A) and (B) and $n = 5$ for (C). Significance of differences was analysed with one-way ANOVA and the post-hoc comparisons Dunnett's test.

breast cancer cells [33]. Our findings suggesting that cancer-endothelium interaction in the presence of platelets can be inhibited by P2Y₁₂ antagonists, stays in agreement with experiments proving that cancer cells co-incubated with platelets from ticagrelor-treated mice exhibit reduced adhesion to endothelium [33]. We also proved that even in the absence of platelets, adhesion of breast cancer cells MDA-MB-231 and colon cancer cells LoVo to

endothelium can be blocked by inhibiting P2Y₁₂ receptor. However, both lines differ in response to P2Y₁₂ agonists and also in efficiency of adhesion to different endothelial cell line. Similar blocking effect of P2Y₁₂ antagonization was observed during cancer invasiveness through endothelium monolayer, which stays in agreement with theories about anti-metastatic properties of P2Y₁₂ receptor inhibition [31–34].

Role of AR agonists in cancer cell interaction with endothelium is more complicated. It is commonly accepted that A_{2B} is involved in tumor cell proliferation, metastasis, angiogenesis, and immune suppression. A_{2B} and A₃ are the only AR subtypes that are overexpressed in cancer tissues in comparison to normal tissues [35]. A_{2A} may be both pro- and anti-tumoral. Inhibition of A_{2A} results in blocking proliferation in tumor microenvironment [36], but increased tumor growth of melanoma and bladder carcinomas was observed after A_{2A} knockout [37].

In our work AR agonists are effective in blocking cancer cell adhesion to endothelium but only in the presence of platelets, which may be the result of blocking platelet activation thus leading to inhibition of platelet-dependent increased adhesion of cancer cells. In the absence of platelets NECA increased interaction between endothelium and MDA-MB-231, when in the case of LoVo adhesion to HMEC-1 can be blocked by both HE-NECA and NECA. This observation is unexpected, since AR agonists are believed to stimulate cancer cells adhesion and migration [35], but some experiments prove otherwise, suggesting that AR agonists, including NECA, inhibit tumor cell invasion via receptor-independent mechanisms [38].

We observed that short time of AR agonization of cancer cells may have no effect on interaction with endothelium or slightly inhibits this process. In contrast to adhesion, AR agonists stimulate cancer cell migration through endothelium monolayer independently of being specific to A_{2A} or A_{2B}, with the highest efficiency after incubation with MRE0094. P2Y₁₂ antagonists attenuate AR agonists-dependent stimulation of migration. This observation proves theories that although antitumor effect of AR antagonists occurs via the A_{2B} rather A_{2A}, simultaneous antagonism of both AR subtypes can be even better approach. In fact mixed A_{2A}/A_{2B} antagonists like AB928 26 and PBF-1129 are now on clinical trials in breast, ovarian, lung, and gastrointestinal cancer [44].

In conclusion, our findings suggest that constitutive secretion of PDI from endothelial cells is independent from antagonization of P2Y₁₂ or agonization of AR. Meanwhile secretion of PDI from thrombin stimulated endothelial cells or platelets can be inhibited by P2Y₁₂ receptor antagonists, but AR agonists attenuate PDI secretion mainly from platelets. Blocking of thrombin-dependent activation of platelets, probably by affecting PDI secretion and integrin activation, may result in diminished interaction between platelets and endothelium and also in inhibition of platelet-stimulated adhesion of cancer cells to endothelium. However using AR agonists to block platelet-dependent cancer adhesion to endothelium has its disadvantages since these factors after long-time incubation may stimulate cancer cells migration through endothelial monolayer thus leading to increased metastasis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest with the contents of this article.

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Abbreviations

AR	adenosine receptor
ARC	cangrelor AR-C69931MX
PDI	Protein Disulfide Isomerase
PM	prasugler metabolite

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2020.03.143>.

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